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Role of Electronic-Learning in Student-centered Learning In Nursing And Midwifery Education

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ABSTRACT

The student-centered approach to learning has gained prominence due to its effectiveness in improving learner engagement and outcomes. It emphasizes active participation, autonomy, and ownership of the learning process. E-learning, defined as the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in education, has become a vital component of student-centered learning (SCL). It enables learners to study at their own pace, access resources anytime and anywhere, and receive real-time feedback. Despite its numerous benefits, many institutions have yet to fully integrate e-learning into their pedagogical practices. This paper highlights the role of e-learning in enhancing student-centered learning, outlines its importance in improving educational outcomes, and recommends strategies for its effective utilization in nursing and midwifery education.

Keywords: e-learning, student-centered learning, Moodle, pedagogy, students

INTRODUCTION

Teaching and learning have evolved significantly over the years. The need to actively involve learners in the educational process has led to the adoption of student-centered learning (SCL), where the learner becomes the central focus. In some literature, this is also referred to as the learner-centered approach. Unlike traditional teacher-centered methods, SCL emphasizes active engagement, autonomy, and collaboration. According to Lindsay (2006), modern education increasingly emphasizes shared responsibility between teachers and learners in determining how teaching and learning occur. The ultimate goal of SCL is to make the teacher progressively less central, while empowering students to take ownership of their learning. Parker (2018) further notes that SCL prioritizes the meaningful needs and development of students, rather than treating course content as the sole endpoint.

E-learning, defined as the use of ICT in the delivery of instruction, has become a powerful enabler of SCL. It allows students to learn at their own pace, engage in interactive activities, self-assess, and access resources anytime and anywhere. E-learning refers to 'the use of Internet technologies to deliver a broad array of solutions that enhances knowledge and performance' (Rosenberg, 2001). Rapid advancement in Information Technology has led to the emergence of using newer tools for transferring knowledge to students (Sarvestan et al., 2019). A study by Barker et al., (2013) in Nairobi- Kenya found that students felt that 'e-learning' is here to stay. Noorbhai (2020) observed that education has evolved and adapted through the digital and electronic ages. Indeed, over the past decade, the rapid developments and growth of information and communication technology (ICT) have had a profound influence on nursing education. E-learning has grown tremendously has been integrated into education and training.

Some studies were conducted on use of E-learning in nursing and midwifery education in different parts of the world. Siabah et al (2023) identified and synthesized theories that support the design and delivery of digital learning interventions in nursing and midwifery education. This systematic review found that a range of theories that support the design and delivery on digital learning interventions in nursing and midwifery education. While a single theory, the Technology Acceptance

Model, tended to dominate the literature, the evidence base is peppered with numerous theoretical models that need to be examined more rigorously to ascertain their utility in improving the design or implementation of digital forms of learning to improve pedagogical research and practice in nursing and midwifery.

Pourghaznein et al (2015) studied the effects of e-learning, lectures, and role playing on nursing students' knowledge acquisition, retention and satisfaction. The study selected sixty nursing students as an experiment and control groups during two consecutive semesters. A questionnaire containing three parts was used to assess demographics, learning and satisfaction statuses. The questionnaire also included a final open ended question to evaluate the students' ideas about the whole course. The results show that the mean scores of posttest were 16.13 ± 1.37 using role playing, 15.50 ± 1.44 using e-learning and 16.45 ± 1.23 using lectures. The differences between the mean scores of posttest and pretest were 12.84 ± 1.43 , 12.56 ± 1.57 , and 13.73 ± 1.53 in the mentioned methods, respectively.

Mambwe and Tembe (2021) undertook a study exploring students' experiences of E-learning in midwifery course: a qualitative study involving nursing students taking midwifery course at Rusangu University in Zambia. The study used a cross-sectional design with a qualitative approach. A mixture of 60 third year and fourth year Nursing students taking Midwifery as a course participated in the study through 6 Focus Group discussions. The study found that students residing in rural places faced challenges of poor internet connectivity due to weak signal strength. They could fail to participate during interactive virtual class due to uncharged electronic gadgets or interrupted session due to power outages. Some had neither Personal Computers nor a smart phone to enable them access learning materials.

Riner, Wainpa, and Beyand .(2020) carried out a case study which describes the use of e-learning in a new graduate program in nursing and midwifery education in Liberia, a developing country recovering from a decade long internal conflict and more recently an Ebola epidemic. The program was established to prepare the educator workforce with current educational concepts and practices as well as health information. Issues involved in making the hardware and internet access are addressed. Through the voices of eleven graduate students who were also nurse and midwife instructors in education facilities throughout the country, perceptions of using e-learning for course work as well as the experience of beginning to use technology in teaching pre-service students are identified. Sustainment and expansion of E - learning challenges are addressed.

Yangoz (2017) carried out a review to examine the effect of e-learning program in nursing education. Akdeniz University electronic databases center including MEDLINE, CINAHL, Sciencedirect, Cochrane library were searched published studies in English with "e-learning, nursing education, nursing students" key words and 554 articles were reached by the search results. By the analysis, published 2011-2016, the original six manuscripts have been sampled. A cross-over design study examined the effect of lecture and e-learning methods were compared, no significant difference was found between two methods. The effect of using e-learning versus lecture of nursing students was examined. Students indicated to be pleased with the e-learning program.

This paper explores the role of e-learning in enhancing student-centered learning, particularly in nursing and midwifery education. The main objective of this paper is to highlight the role of e-learning in student-centered learning. Specifically, it seeks to:

1. Explain how e-learning enhances student-centered learning.
2. Identify the importance of e-learning in improving student-centered learning.
3. Recommend strategies for integrating e-learning into student-centered approaches.
 1. The need to enhance the learning process to ensure effective outcomes.
 2. The growing emphasis on achieving student-centered learning approaches.
 3. The increasing demand for flexible, anytime-anywhere learning opportunities.

E-Learning in Perspective

E-learning, short for electronic learning, refers to the use of digital technologies to deliver, support, and enhance teaching and learning. Unlike traditional face-to-face instruction, e-learning leverages computers, mobile devices, and the internet to provide flexible and accessible education. The Learning Skills Development Agency (2017) defines e-learning as the use of electronic technology to deliver, support, and enhance teaching and learning.

E-learning refers to the use of various kinds of electronic media and information and communication technologies (ICT) in education. E-learning is an inclusive terminology that encompasses all forms of educational technology that electronically or technologically support learning and teaching. Depending on whether a particular aspect, component or delivery method is given emphasis, e-learning may be termed technology-enhanced learning (TEL), computer-based training (CBT), internet-based training (IBT), web-based training (WBT), online education, virtual education, or digital educational collaboration (ABUAD, 2020).

Common forms of e-learning include computer-based training, web-based lessons, and online courses. With advances in technology, lessons can be accessed anytime and anywhere, often enriched with multimedia such as text, graphics, sound, and animation. E-learning can be formal (structured lessons) or informal (e.g., discussions, emails, online forums) (Rajan, 2017).

Bloomfield and Jones (2013) describe e-learning as a dynamic and innovative way to provide learning opportunities, enabling students to participate in real-time lectures and discussions or access materials asynchronously. Keefe and Wharrad (2012) add that e-learning enhances knowledge and skills through tutorials, simulations, case-based learning, and game-based modules.

Learning Platforms

Several terms are used to describe e-learning platforms:

- LMS (Learning Management System)
- LCMS (Learning Content Management System)
- VLE (Virtual Learning Environment)
- PLE (Personal Learning Environment)
- MLE (Managed Learning Environment)
- MOOC (Massive Open Online Courses)

Among these, Moodle is one of the most widely used LMS platforms. Moodle (Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment) is an open-source system that allows educators to create customized online courses, manage content, and facilitate interactive learning.

Through e-learning, students can engage interactively, receive real-time feedback, and self-evaluate in preparation for assessments. Simulations also allow learners to practice practical skills in science and technology. The vast resources available online further enrich the learning experience.

Student-Centered Learning

Student-centered learning is an approach where the entire learning experience is designed around the learner. Courses must be user-friendly, relevant, and flexible, allowing learners to navigate content easily, select areas of interest, and engage with real-life examples (Timothy, 2015).

Student-centered learning is a teaching method that shifts the focus from teachers to students, aiming to build meaningful and constructive connections with students' interests while keeping them engaged and motivated. It can be described as the opposite of the traditional instructional method, known as teacher-centered learning, which is still adopted by the striking majority of today's educators (ETA, 2025). Throughout the 20th century, student-centered learning gradually gained ground and received increasing recognition for the way it promotes autonomy and active learning by making students the leaders of their own learning process (ETA, 2025).

Students learn in diverse ways and benefit from guidance rather than prescription. Active participation in the learning process is therefore essential for knowledge acquisition and skill development. E-learning supports this by providing flexible, accessible, and responsive platforms that empower learners to take control of their education.

Benefits of Student-Centered Learning

- Students can work independently or in small groups, either at school or at home.
- Learners gain access to a wider range of materials.
- Students are actively involved in what they study.
- Learners take ownership of their education.
- Motivation and commitment are enhanced.

The teacher's role in SCL shifts to that of a facilitator or guide, helping students develop strategies, refine research abilities, and build problem-solving skills.

Table 1: Difference Between Teacher-Centered and Student-Centered Learning

Teacher-Centered	Student-Centered
Low level of student choice	High level of student choice
Students are passive	Students are active
Decisions rest with the teacher	Decisions involve the student

Role of E-Learning in Student-Centered Learning

The importance of e-learning in advancing student-centered learning cannot be overstated. E-learning incorporates ICT to support flexible, interactive, and personalized education. It aligns closely with the principles of SCL by empowering learners to take control of their educational journey.

Key roles of e-learning in student-centered learning include:

1. **Self-paced learning** – Students can progress at their own speed, choosing when and how to engage with content.
2. **Real-time feedback** – Learners can interact with instructors and receive immediate responses, enhancing understanding.
3. **Access to updated materials** – E-learning platforms provide multimedia resources such as videos, documents, and simulations that are regularly updated.
4. **Self-assessment and evaluation** – Online quizzes and exercises allow students to monitor their progress and prepare for examinations.
5. **Learning convenience** – Students can access lessons anytime and anywhere, eliminating rigid classroom schedules.
6. **Peer-to-peer learning** – Platforms enable interaction among students, fostering collaborative knowledge exchange.
7. **Collaborative learning** – Group tasks and problem-solving activities can be facilitated online, encouraging teamwork and critical thinking.

CONCLUSION

E-learning is transforming the learning process by making education more flexible, interactive, and student-driven. Its integration into student-centered learning enhances efficiency, improves learner performance, and prepares students for lifelong learning. For nursing and midwifery education, where competence and practical skills are essential, e-learning offers opportunities for simulation, collaboration, and continuous feedback. Institutions are therefore encouraged to adopt e-learning tools and strategies as a core component of student-centered pedagogy.

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